

Degradation and biocompatibility of 3D-printed PLA reinforced with WS₂ nanotubes for bone scaffold applications

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Research Motivation

Application

- Anchoring equipment for orthopedic implants and fractures
- Scaffolds in favor of a substrate for bone growth

Disadvantages of today's implants

- ❖ Risk of implant rejection
- ❖ Stress shielding
- ❖ Additional surgery is required to remove them
- ❖ One size fits all

Bone Scaffold Requirements

1. Mechanical properties

Equal to or exceeding the original bone

2. Degradation rate

In alignment with bone growth

3. Biocompatibility

Biocompatible implants

Poly(lactic Acid) – (PLA)

- Thermoplastic
- Biodegradable
- Non-toxic
- Biocompatible
- Produce from renewable resources such as corn, sugarcane and starch

PLA Degradation Mechanism

Hydrolysis degradation

Enzymatic degradation

Inorganic Nanotubes of WS₂

- Was synthesized and first observed by the Reshef Tenne's group in 1992
- Individual layers of the metal dichalcogenides MX₂
- Relatively possess good mechanical properties
- Non-toxic

Degradation Test Samples Preparation

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Results

Mass Change

➤ $Mass\ Loss\% = 100\% - \left[\frac{(m_i - m_f)}{m_i} \times 100\% \right]$

Mass Change

Mechanism of hydrolytic degradation

Size Exclusion Chromatography (SEC)

$$PDI = \frac{M_w}{M_n}$$

Micro Vickers Hardness Test

➤ Using relatively low loads, surface hardness properties are mostly determined

Mechanical Properties Tests

Tensile Test

➤ Mostly bulk mechanical properties

Biocompatibility Test

Cell viability of the filaments pre-printing

Relative metabolic activity of the cells for the 3D-printed samples

Biocompatibility Test

SEM images of MC3T3 cells on 3D printed samples in 20 micron bar under SE mode. a. Neat PLA and b. PLA/INT-WS₂ nanocomposite before cells siding. c. Neat PLA sample and d. PLA/INT-WS₂ after cells attachment.

- Tensile, thermal, and SEC analyses confirm PLA/INT-WS₂ degradation, with mass, hardness, and morphology indicates that the material underwent bulk degradation mechanism.
- Ultimate tensile strength remains 2.6 times higher than the maximum stress experienced during normal walking on a femur, after three months of degradation.
- The nanocomposite exhibits excellent biocompatibility, supporting cell growth and viability.
- Overall, the PLA/INT-WS₂ nanocomposite holds significant promise as a 3D-printed material for bone regeneration applications.

Future work

- Conduct longer-term studies to fully understand the degradation behavior of PLA/INT-WS₂ over extended periods, as bone healing can take several months to years depending on the injury.

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Any Questions?

